

OXIDE-OXIDE CMCS PREPARED BY ELECTROPHORETIC INFILTRATION (EPI) OF NEXTEL™ PREFORMS

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SUMMARY: Oxide-oxide ceramic matrix composites are candidates for numerous applications in high temperature environments. Conventional manufacturing routes are based on slurry infiltration and filament winding. Alternatively, electrophoretic infiltration (EPI) of finely dispersed oxide particles into woven fiber mats appears promising. In this paper, the results of the EPI of Nextel™720 and Nextel™650 (3M) woven fabrics with alumina, zirconia and mullite (precursor) powders are presented. Slurries made up of submicron-sized oxide powders, ethanol as dispersion medium and appropriate dispersants were formulated in order to achieve repulsive interactions in the particle-fiber system and, thus, high stability of the slurry, high electrophoretic mobility of the particles and a high level of infiltration. Among oxide matrices, mullite has attracted considerable interest, owing to its excellent creep resistance and low modulus. One promising approach to densify the mullite matrix at temperatures not causing fiber degradation is to fill the fibre preform with a diphasic mullite precursor for which densification and crystallization occur simultaneously in the appropriate temperature range. This paper reports for the first time the electrophoretic infiltration of Nextel™720 woven fibre mats with SIRAL 28M, a commercial mullite precursor (SASOL Germany GmbH). This precursor consists of boehmite and amorphous silica (Al_2O_3 : SiO_2 mullite stoichiometric ratio) coexisting at the nanometer level. It is completely converted to orthorhombic mullite at 1300°C. The results show that EPI of Nextel™ preforms with submicron-sized oxide powders can be successfully used to produce green bodies which can be sintered at 1300°C forming porous matrices. The combination of EPI as a simple processing method and the concept of porous matrices for enabling damage tolerance without the use of a fiber coating presents new opportunities for low-cost, high-performance CMCs.

KEYWORDS: ceramic matrix composites, electrophoretic infiltration, mullite, alumina

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic composites with continuous oxide fibers and an oxide matrix have the potential for combining high damage tolerance with extreme temperature resistance. Their inherent stability in oxidizing environments and their low weight makes them candidate materials for components of spacecraft, aeroengines, power plants and chemical reactors. Most manufacturing processes combine liquid infiltration (slurry infiltration and filament winding, vacuum infiltration of fabrics) with subsequent high temperature processing [1]. A challenge remains to develop reliable, versatile, and more cost-effective processing routes for oxide-oxide CMCs.

Electrophoresis has already gained world-wide acceptance in numerous industrial applications as a method for the deposition of coatings (electrophoretic deposition – EPD) [2]. EPD has the ability to cover recessed portions of parts having a complex shape. Therefore, another application of electrophoresis is gaining increasing interest: the infiltration of fiber preforms with matrix material for composite production (electrophoretic infiltration – EPI) [3]. In the present work, we used alumina and zirconia powders and a diphasic mullite precursor for the EPI of Nextel™720 and Nextel™650 woven fabrics. Mullite emerges as a particularly attractive matrix material for CMCs, owing to its excellent creep resistance and low modulus. Its generally sluggish sintering kinetics below 1300°C suggests adequate microstructural stability for high-temperature applications up to 1200°C. On the other hand, temperatures above 1300°C are required to achieve the requisite bonding between submicrometer mullite particles, yet most commercial oxide fibers are susceptible to microstructural degradation at

these temperatures. One promising approach to densify the matrix without causing fiber degradation is to fill the fiber preform with a mullite precursor for which densification and crystallization occur simultaneously in the appropriate temperature range. In this work, we attempt for the first time the electrophoretic infiltration (EPI) of Nextel™720 woven fiber mats with the mullite precursor SIRAL 28M.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: Woven fabrics (8H satin weave) of Nextel™720 and Nextel™650 oxide fibers (3M Co., St. Paul, MN) were used. The nominal fiber diameter was 10-12 μm with 400 fibers (Nextel™720) and 750 fibers (Nextel™650) per roving. The as-received woven fabrics were cut into pieces of 5x5 cm^2 and desized at 700°C prior to infiltration. According to Lange et al. [4], the particle-to-fiber diameter ratio (R) for packing powders within reinforcement preforms should be $R < 0.05$. Therefore, we chose AKP 50 (Sumitomo Corp.) with a nominal particle size ranging from 100 to 300 nm as alumina powder. A yttria-stabilized zirconia nanopowder (TZ 8Y) was supplied by Tosoh Corp.

The diphasic mullite precursor SIRAL 28M used in this study was provided by Sasol Germany. It consists of pseudo-boehmite and an amorphous silica phase, coexisting at nanometer level in the mullite stoichiometric ratio. SIRAL 28M was calcined (1150°C, 5 hrs) prior to processing [5] in order to reduce its high specific surface area and to convert pseudo-boehmite into transition aluminas. This calcination step led to agglomerates up to 25 μm in size. In order to destroy the agglomerates and to achieve a submicrometer particle size distribution, the ethanolic suspension of the calcined precursor was milled for 3 hours in a LabStar LS1 mill (Netzsch Feinmahltechnik, Selb, Germany) using 0.5 mm and 0.3 mm YTZ milling balls.

Suspensions were prepared in ethanol (Merck, GR for analysis) supported by high-intensity ultrasonic treatment (Branson Sonifier W-450). Solids loadings of the suspensions were in the range of 10-30 wt%. The pH was adjusted with HNO_3 and NH_4OH or triethanolamine (all Merck, GR for analysis). Organic substances used as dispersants in this study included 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (Merck, GR for analysis) and citric acid monohydrate (Fluka, puriss. p.a.).

Methods: The success of the electrophoretic infiltration method largely depends on the nature and strength of the particle-particle and particle-fiber interaction forces. The aim of suspension optimization is to gain control over these interactions. There are two suspension characteristics that are desirable for the EPI approach. The first is a high degree of stability since agglomerates would have difficulty in penetrating into the small inter-fiber gaps, thus preventing further infiltration. The second desirable characteristic is a high zeta potential of the particles. The zeta potential reflects the surface charge for a specific material in a fluid medium and is sensitive to the adsorption of ionic dispersant species at the particle-solvent interface. It directly impacts the state of dispersion and the electrophoretic mobility. For oxides in amphiprotic solvents the surface charge will be determined mainly by adsorption or desorption of protons. Thus, to ensure good infiltration, the measurement and optimization of pH, zeta potential and particle size distribution are crucial.

Ethanol was chosen as the suspending medium because the problem of electrolytic gas evolution is greatly reduced compared to water. On the other hand, both ethanol and water are neutral amphiprotic solvents and acid-base chemistry principles remain valid for ethanol. In this paper, pH* refers to operational readings of a pH meter (pmx 2000, wtw Weilheim, Germany) using a pH combination electrode calibrated with standard aqueous buffer solutions. The electrokinetic sonic amplitude (ESA) which is proportional to the zeta potential was measured using the ESA 8000 system (Matec Applied Sciences). The particle size distribution of suspensions was determined by photon correlation spectroscopy (Zetasizer 3000HS, Malvern Instruments).

Figure 1 shows the basic configuration of the electrophoretic cell. The electrodes were stainless steel plates with the nonconducting fiber weave attached to the deposition electrode. Infiltration conditions

were 100 V, with a gap of 2 cm between electrodes, i.e. a mean field strength of 50 V/ cm, applied for typical infiltration times in the range of 1-3 min for a single weave in constant voltage mode. After removing the deposition electrode from the cell, the attached green body was allowed to dry at ambient atmosphere and finally was taken away from the electrode. The green bodies were pressureless sintered in air at 1300°C for 1 hr with a heating rate of 10°C/ min.

Fig. 1 Electrophoretic cell

Fig. 2 ESA measurement

The microstructural development of the composites was monitored by means of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDX) on polished cross-sections. The samples were infiltrated with a low-viscous epoxy resin before cutting, grinding and polishing. The phases present in the sintered matrices were determined using x-ray powder diffraction (XRD).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Alumina matrices: The suspended alumina powder particles had an initial positive net charge. In order to increase their zeta potential, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (4HBA) was selected as dispersant. The optimum dispersant concentration was determined by measuring the ESA signal of the suspension as a function of the amount of dispersant added. As may be seen in Fig. 2, addition of 4HBA results in a considerable rise of the ESA signal, leading to an optimum concentration of 4 mass %.

Fig. 3 Nextel™720/ alumina, green body

Fig. 4 Nextel™720/ alumina, sintered

Green bodies produced with this optimized suspension were homogeneous and free of macroscopic cracks (Fig. 3). The microstructure of a sintered sample is shown in Fig. 4. Excellent intra-tow infiltration and a uniformly developed alumina matrix with fine, homogeneous porosity and no shrinkage flaws can be readily seen. The efficient processing of CMCs requires the infiltration of three-dimensional preforms consisting of at least two fabric planes. In the present work up to four Nextel™720 8H fabric sheets were attached to the deposition electrode and infiltrated in a single run. Figure 5 shows a typical micrograph of a sintered three-layer composite specimen. Full intra-tow and inter-tow infiltration has been achieved, indicating the high throw power of the EPI method. A notable feature is the presence of matrix cracks perpendicular to the fabric plane. Their concentration in matrix-rich regions suggests the possibility of reducing the extent of cracking by adjusting the fiber content of the composite.

Fig. 5 Nextel™720/ alumina, 6 ply, sintered

For applications in corrosive environments, the presence of silica-containing phases (like mullite in Nextel™720) in a high temperature ceramic matrix composite is not desirable [6]. Compared to Nextel™720, Nextel™650 fibers containing alumina with 10 wt% ZrO₂ and 1 wt% Y₂O₃ are the better choice for these applications. As with Nextel™720, EPI worked equally well with Nextel™650 fiber weaves in this study. The similar behaviour of alumina and zirconia concerning the adsorption of the dispersant 4HBS (Fig. 2) should permit the co-infiltration of both powders, resulting in a matrix composition adapted to the fiber composition. Figure 6 shows the result of the co-infiltration of a Nextel™650 fiber weave with a suspension of 80 wt% alumina and 20 wt% zirconia. EDX confirms the presence of both phases in the matrix, further experiments to investigate the homogeneity of their distribution are in progress.

Fig. 6 Nextel™650/ alumina+zirconia, sintered

Mullite matrices: Though already successfully used in slurry infiltration [7], Siral 28M has – to the best of the authors’ knowledge – never been used in EPI before. The advantage of using diphasic mullite precursor powders like Siral 28M is that there is no need to create heterocoagulated “composite” particles or mixing silica and alumina species in suspension homogeneously on a nanometer scale. The calcined and milled Siral 28M showed no electrophoretic mobility, indicating that its natural pH in ethanol is near the isoelectric point (IEP). Adjusting the suspension pH* to values away from the IEP led to stable suspensions with the desired submicron particle size distributions. These suspensions with pH* 4.5 (HNO₃ added) and 6.8 (triethanolamine + 0.5 wt% citric acid as dispersant added) were used in cathodic and anodic infiltration of Nextel™720 fiber weaves, respectively. As far as the infiltration and the microstructure of the resulting composites are concerned, no significant differences between the two modes were found.

Fig. 7 Nextel™720/ mullite, sintered

Fig. 8 Nextel™720/ mullite, sintered

Figure 7 shows the good intra-tow infiltration, Fig. 8 indicates the fine porosity (pores ~ 1 μm in diameter) of the mullite matrix within the fiber bundles. An examination at lower magnifications shows good levels of inter-tow infiltration, but reveals also the presence of cracklike shrinkage flaws within the matrix (Fig. 9). The crack pattern observed may well be caused by drying microcracks which developed further due to volume reduction during reaction sintering of the mullite precursor. Further work on the optimization of processing steps will address this issue. The X-ray diffraction patterns (Fig. 10) clearly show the complete conversion (within the detection limits of XRD) of the calcined diphasic precursor Siral 28M to orthorhombic mullite in the sintered matrix material.

Fig. 9 Nextel™720/ mullite, sintered

Fig. 10 Conversion of calcined Siral 28M to mullite

CONCLUSIONS

Nextel™720 and Nextel™650 woven fabrics have been electrophoretically infiltrated with ethanolic suspensions of commercially available alumina, zirconia and mullite (precursor) powders. It has been shown that EPI has the throw power to infiltrate several fabric sheets in a single run, resulting in composites with good intra-tow- and inter-tow infiltration and fine, homogeneous matrix porosities. The electrophoretic infiltration with a suspension of a diphasic mullite precursor powder allows densification and conversion into mullite at temperatures compatible with fiber stability. Further investigations are required to reduce the extent of matrix cracking. EPI is a relatively simple, versatile, fast and economical processing method which – in combination with the concept of porous matrices for enabling damage tolerance – presents new opportunities for low-cost, high-performance oxide-oxide CMCs.

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